

A Student-Centric Evaluation of the Awareness, Acceptance, Relevance, and Dissemination of the Student Affairs and Services VMGO in the Framework of San Isidro College

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ABSTRACT

Student affairs and services typically support and enhance the overall student experience by providing various services and programs that promote student development and well-being. The research focuses on the gap in the students' understanding of the role and purpose of student affairs and services. The study is anchored on the student development principle, which emphasizes the importance of creating a supportive and inclusive school. The study utilized the descriptive research design, employing an adopted research questionnaire and utilizing a multi-stage sampling to select respondents from the seven schools of San Isidro College. The study revealed that students are well aware of the VMGO of the office of SAS, with high ratings in awareness, acceptance and understanding, relevance, and dissemination, though areas like student welfare services and orientation processes need improvement. The ANOVA test indicates a balanced perception across these dimensions, suggesting a well-integrated office of the SAS framework. However, there is a need to enhance specific aspects to further boost student engagement and support, particularly in student services awareness and individual responsibility for VMGO realization.

Keywords: *student affairs and services, student evaluation, vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO)*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The school's vision and mission are two of the most crucial aspects in designing a successful program and activities. However, people take them for granted and consider them relatively trivial. If written correctly, a school or office's vision and mission can provide clarity and direction. Uncertainty in the school's vision and goal might make it difficult to establish priorities and contribute to ongoing disagreements. The stakeholders must understand the office's vision and

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objective, especially the students (Center for School Change, n.d.). The student affairs and services (SAS) vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO) are aligned with the institution's VMGO as they both aim to facilitate the holistic development and success of the students. The SAS is designed to provide support and resources to enable students to achieve their academic, personal, and career goals, which ultimately contributes to the overall mission and goals of the institution (Tan, 2021). The VMGO of the SAS was developed during the Academic Year 2021-2022 and was implemented during the Academic Year 2022-2023.

Moreover, students should be aware of the VMGO of the SAS because it helps them understand the purpose and direction of the department. This knowledge can help students utilize the services and resources, improving their college experience. In order to enhance academic instruction and promote holistic student development for active participation in nation-building, Higher Education institutions (HEIs) must offer a variety of student-centered activities and services. It must answer the need to meet societal needs, encourage cooperation and equity, and uphold academic excellence. (UNESCO, 2002).

Being aware of the vision of SAS provides students with an understanding of the desired future state of the department. This information allows students to see the overarching goals of the department, which may include creating a supportive campus environment or promoting student academic success (Cascolan & Venture, 2019; Aquino & Rivano, 2022). The mission of SAS outlines the department's purpose and values. Students who are familiar with this information will better understand the department's objectives and how they relate to their personal goals. The goals and objectives of SAS give students specific targets for the department. If students know these goals, they can use the services and resources that align with their needs and interests (Constantino et al., 2020).

The relevance of the VMGO of SAS to the students is that it provides a framework for the department to support student success. If students understand these frameworks, they can proactively seek assistance and guidance from the department, making the most of their college experience (Villanca et al., 2020). Overall, the VMGO of the SAS should reflect a commitment to supporting and enhancing the overall student experience and promoting student success both inside and outside the classroom (Ludeman et al., 2009). The study focuses on the need for students to understand SAS's role and purpose. Additionally, there could be confusion or miscommunication about the department's specific goals and objectives. Without a clear understanding of the VMGO, it may not be easy to allocate resources effectively, plan programs and services, and evaluate the impact of initiatives. Therefore, conducting the study can help identify gaps in information and update strategies to better communicate and engage stakeholders in SAS's work.

In light of this, the purpose of this study is to examine the students' awareness, acceptance, and relevance of the VMGO of the SAS of San Isidro College.

Theoretical Framework

The study anchors on the Student Development Theory. This theory emphasizes the importance of creating a supportive and inclusive campus environment that fosters the students' cognitive, emotional, social, and ethical development (Astin, 1984). It also emphasizes the importance of understanding the diverse needs and backgrounds of the students and creating programs and services that cater to their unique needs. By using this theory, research can evaluate

the effectiveness of the current vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO) of the Student Affairs and Services (SAS) in promoting student development and success (LePeau, 2015).

The student development theory is relevant in the study involving the student's evaluation of the VMGO of the SAS of an institution because it provides a framework for understanding how students learn and grow during their college experience. The theory suggests that students' progress through various stages of development, each with unique challenges and opportunities for growth (MacDonald, 2013). By understanding these stages, educators and administrators can better tailor their programs and services to meet the needs of students at different points in their development.

Additionally, the student development theory emphasizes the importance of holistic education, recognizing that students are complex individuals with various personal and academic needs. This can inform the design and implementation of SAS that address academic achievement and social, emotional, and spiritual growth (Evans et al., 2009). Thus, incorporating the student development theory in the evaluation of SAS can provide insights into how well the institution supports students' growth and development and identify areas for improvement to better meet students' needs.

Vision and Mission of the Student Affairs and Services

The SAS has for its vision:

“A responsive Student Affairs and Services unit with a zeal for excellence in the delivery of relevant activities and programs for students’ holistic welfare and development.”

The SAS has for its mission:

“To create an inclusive and collaborative student-centered activities and programs that support students’ journey of learning, discovery, and engagement.”

The SAS has for its goals and objectives:

1. *“To provide relevant activities and programs that maximize students’ potentials and holistic development”*
2. *“To develop a culture of service, prayer and care for others and the rest of creation”*
3. *“To foster an environment of responsibility and accountability, learning and collaboration among stakeholders”*

The design of the conceptual framework capitalizes on evaluating the SAS's VMGO to reveal students' assessment of the awareness, acceptance, and relevance of the VMGO of the SAS.

Statement of the Problem

This study examines the student's awareness, acceptance, and relevance of the vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO) of the Student Affairs and Services (SAS). Specifically, it answers the following:

1. What is the students' level of awareness of the VMGO of the Student Affairs and Services?

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2. What is the students' level of acceptance of the VMGO of the Student Affairs and Services?
3. What is the students' level of relevance of the VMGO of the Student Affairs and Services?
4. What is the students' level of dissemination of the VMGO of the Student Affairs and Services?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive research design employing the quantitative analysis based on the results surveyed by the college students of the seven (7) schools in the college department. San Isidro College (SIC) is a private catholic institution in Malaybalay City that served as the research locale for the survey questionnaire. The study participants were students enrolled during the Academic Year 2023-2024. The study used multi-stage sampling, using stratified and purposive sampling. The study groups the students by school and randomly selects the study participants.

Table 1.
Demographic distribution of the respondent of the study (N=735).

Department	f	%
School of Accountancy	40	5.4
School of Arts and Sciences	44	6.0
School of Business Administration	73	9.9
School of Education	157	21.4
School of Engineering	89	12.1
School of Information Technology	37	5.0
School of Nursing and Midwifery	294	40.1

The principal instrument adapted for the study is the questionnaire developed by Tan (2021), containing three (3) categories that use a 5-point Likert scale to evaluate the VMGO of the SAS. The first category is *awareness*, with eight (8) statements reflecting the students' awareness of the VMGO of SAS, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.723. The second category is *acceptance*, with eight (8) statements reflecting the students' level of acceptance on the VGMO of the SAS, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.711. The third category is *relevance*, with seventeen (17) statements reflecting the level of relevance of the VMGO of the SAS to the students', with a Cronbach alpha of 0.789. Lastly, the fourth category is *dissemination*, with eight (8) statements reflecting the level of dissemination of the VMGO of the SAS to the students, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.767. The questionnaire has an overall Cronbach alpha of 0.772. The quantitative data was treated using descriptive statistics, specifically the mean and standard deviation, and the ANOVA test was used to compare the four categories.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents the summary of the students' evaluation towards their level of awareness regarding the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of the office of Student Affairs and Services (SAS).

Table 2.
Summary of student evaluation on their awareness regarding the VMGO of SAS.

Statements	Mean	Qual. Int.
The vision of the program which is to provide an atmosphere necessary for the holistic development of students.	3.70	AV
The mission of the SAS which is tasked with the management and supervision of student and personnel services and activities complementing academic instruction and intended to facilitate holistic student development for active involvement in nation building.	3.69	AV
The Student Affairs and Services Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives declare the difference it seeks to make in the community through the students and graduates.	3.69	AV
The Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives are displayed in bulletin boards, printed in catalogs, manuals and other printed materials, and broadcasted in the Student Affairs and Services and/or school web site and/or social media pages such as Facebook, Google+, among others.	3.69	AV
The goals and objectives of the SAS which are focused on the realization of the mission and vision.	3.68	AV
The Student Affairs and Services Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives inspire student commitment, engagement and excellence, and help boost the college's performance and overall target.	3.68	AV
The different student welfare services, student development services, and institutional student programs and services are geared towards the attainment of the Student Affairs and Services Vision and Mission.	3.67	AV
The Student Affairs and Services Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives are presented during orientations and assemblies every year or semester.	3.67	AV
Overall	3.69	AV

Legend:

AG – Aware to a great extent AM – Aware to a moderate extent AL – Aware to a little extent
 AV – Aware to a very good extent AF – Aware to a fair extent

The results in Table 2, indicating that students are "*aware to a very good extent*" of the VMGO of the office of SAS, suggest a strong foundational awareness among the student body. The highest awareness factor was the vision of the program aiming for the holistic development of students, which emphasizes that students recognize the importance of a supportive environment conducive to their overall growth (Tan, 2021). However, the lowest awareness factors point to a need for better communication regarding the specific student welfare services and the regular presentation of the VMGO during orientations and assemblies (Sanchez & Olvido, 2024). While students are generally aware of the VMGO, there is room for improvement in ensuring consistent and detailed dissemination of specific services and goals, which could enhance overall student engagement and utilization of available resources (Lacaba & Pelicano, 2016; Escolano, 2021).

Table 3 presents the summary of the students' evaluation towards their level of acceptance and understanding regarding the VMGO of the office of SAS.

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Table 3.

Summary of student evaluation on their acceptance and understanding regarding the VMGO of SAS.

Statements	Mean	Qual. Int.
The Student Affairs and Services Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives inspire student commitment, engagement and excellence, and helps boost the college’s performance and overall target.	3.70	AUV
The Student Affairs and Services Vision and Mission are aligned to the core values that the college wants its students and graduates to exhibit as they perform their tasks.	3.69	AUV
The Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives of the Student Affairs and Services.	3.68	AUV
The Student Affairs and Services Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives are ambitious enough to be exciting but not too ambitious for it to be unachievable	3.68	AUV
The Student Affairs and Services Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives reflects its legal and educational mandate.	3.68	AUV
The words used in the Vision and Mission statements are specific and not open to many interpretations.	3.68	AUV
The Vision and Mission clearly reflects what the SAS hopes its students and graduates to become in the future	3.67	AUV
The responsibility of realizing the Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives in my own capacity.	3.66	AUV
Overall	3.68	AUV

Legend:

AUG – Accepted and Understood to a great extent	AUM – Accepted and Understood to a moderate extent	AUL – Accepted and Understood to a little extent
AUV – Accepted and Understood to a very good extent	AUF – Accepted and Understood to a fair extent	

Table 3 reveals that students' acceptance and understanding of the VMGO of the office of SAS are also rated "*accepted and understood to a very good extent.*" The highest acceptance and understanding factor, inspiring student commitment, engagement, and excellence, implies that the VMGO effectively motivates students and aligns with their aspirations, contributing positively to the college's performance (Tan, 2021). However, the lowest factor, realizing the VMGO in the students' capacity, indicates that while students appreciate the VMGO, they may need help to see their role in achieving these objectives (Clemente et al., 2021). The result suggests that the office of SAS could focus on strategies to empower students to take personal responsibility and actively contribute to the realization of the VMGO (Clemente & Clemente, 2022). The finding is crucial for the study as it highlights the need for student-centric approaches that not only communicate the VMGO but also foster a sense of individual accountability and involvement among students (Aquino & Rivano, 2022).

Table 4 presents the summary of the students' evaluation towards the level of relevance regarding the VMGO of the office of SAS.

Table 4.
Summary of student evaluation on the relevance regarding the VMGO of SAS.

Statements	Mean	Qual. Int.
Provide programs and activities designed to give equal opportunities to differently – abled individuals, indigenous peoples, single parents, and other marginalized groups.	3.72	RV
Ensure the safety and protection of all persons and properties in the campus, maintain and keep the campus clean always, and ensure the availability of outlets that provide sanitary, nutritious and affordable food within the campus	3.71	RV
Provide venue for the spiritual development of students.	3.70	RV
Create an atmosphere conducive to study and learning through proper observance of the school rules and regulations.	3.70	RV
Provide primary health and dental care to students.	3.70	RV
Provide an environment necessary for the holistic development of students.	3.69	RV
Is tasked with the management and supervision of student and personnel services and activities complementing academic instruction and intended to facilitate holistic student development for active involvement in nation building.	3.69	RV
Require service units under the supervision of Student Affairs and Services to prepare and implement programs and activities that are meant to enhance the total personality development of students.	3.68	RV
Encourage all students to join co- and extra – curricular organizations, programs and activities.	3.68	RV
Foster the setting up of activities that train students in the act of self – governance through proper guidance and recognition of organizations with legitimate aims and purposes.	3.67	RV
Promote leadership, cultural and social consciousness.	3.65	RV
Help students acquire skills, attitudes and values that enable them to cooperate with colleagues and other professionals in future careers.	3.63	RV
Assist students to understand themselves and the world better so that they become more effective, more productive students and human beings.	3.63	RV
Promote the development of a sound mind in a healthy body.	3.62	RV
Cultivate the spirit of service to others, and the sense of camaraderie or fellowship for constructive purposes.	3.61	RV
Facilitate the optimum, balanced and harmonious formation and holistic development of students.	3.61	RV
Orient students to the college environment.	3.60	RV
Overall	3.66	RV

Legend:

RG – Relevant to a great extent

RV – Relevant to a very good extent

RM – Relevant to a moderate extent

RF – Relevant to a fair extent

RL – Relevant to a little

extent

Table 4 reveals that students rated the relevance of the VMGO of the office of SAS as "*relevant to a very good extent.*" The highest relevance factor provides programs and activities designed to give equal opportunities to differently-abled individuals, indigenous peoples, single parents, and other marginalized groups, indicating a strong recognition of the inclusivity and comprehensive support provided by the office of SAS (Tan, 2021). However, the lowest factor, the orientation of students to the college environment, suggests that there might be gaps in how new students are introduced to the college's environment and resources (Tan & Prado, 2020; Aquino & Rivano, 2022). The result implies that while the programs are deemed relevant, there may be a need to enhance the orientation processes to ensure all students are adequately prepared and informed about the available support systems, thus improving their initial experience and integration into college life (Escolano, 2021).

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Table 5 presents the summary of the students’ evaluation towards the level of dissemination regarding the VMGO of the office of SAS.

Table 5.
Summary of student evaluation on the dissemination of the VMGO of SAS.

Statements	Mean	Qual. Int.
The Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives through the Student Affairs and Services offices and/or school web site and/or social media pages such as Facebook, Google+, among others.	3.72	DV
The Student Affairs and Services’ Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives during general student orientation every semester and stakeholders’ consultative conference.	3.71	DV
The Student Affairs and Services’ Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives through the school’s journals, bulletins, newsletters, school papers, etc.	3.69	DV
The Student Affairs and Services Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives during class orientation.	3.69	DV
A clear Student Affairs and Services’ Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives.	3.68	DV
The Student Affairs and Services’ Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives through leaflets, brochures and other printed materials.	3.67	DV
The Affairs and Services Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives to all students including special groups such as but not limited to indigenous peoples (IPs), persons with disabilities (PWDs), solo parents, foreign students, among others.	3.66	DV
Overall	3.69	DV

Legend:

DG – Disseminated to a great extent	DM – Disseminated to a moderate extent	DL – Disseminated to a little extent
DV – Disseminated to a very good extent	DF – Disseminated to a fair extent	

Table 5 indicates that the dissemination of the VMGO by the OSAS is rated "*disseminated to a very good extent.*" The highest dissemination factor was through the Student Affairs and Services offices and school website and social media pages, showing the effectiveness of digital platforms in reaching students (Tan, 2021). However, the lowest dissemination factor, targeting all students, including special groups such as Indigenous peoples, persons with disabilities, and solo parents, highlights a need for more targeted communication strategies (Lacaba & Pelicano, 2016; Tan & Prado, 2020). The result implies that while general dissemination is effective, more inclusive approaches are necessary to ensure that all student demographics are equally informed and engaged (Dolipas et al., 2022). The importance of leveraging diverse communication channels to reach all student groups, ensuring that every segment of the student population is included (Talosa et al., 2021).

The one-way ANOVA was performed to compare the students’ level of awareness, acceptance and understanding, relevance, and dissemination of the VMGO of the office of SAS of San Isidro College (SIC). The mean and standard deviation are presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6.

Comparison the of the awareness, acceptance and understanding, relevance, and dissemination level of the students.

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Qual. Int.	F	<i>p</i>
Dissemination	3.69	1.170	DV	0.071	0.975
Awareness	3.69	1.217	AV		
Acceptance and Understanding	3.68	1.180	AUV		
Relevance	3.66	1.138	RV		

As presented in Table 6, the ANOVA was not significant at the $p < 0.05$ level, $F(3,2936) = 0.071$, $p = 0.975$. The result indicates that there is no significant difference between the level of awareness, acceptance and understanding, relevance, and dissemination of the students with regards to the VMGO of the office of SAS in SIC.

The ANOVA test results show no significant difference between these means, indicating a consistent perception across all dimensions. The results uniformity suggests that the office of SAS has successfully integrated the VMGO across various aspects, ensuring a balanced approach. However, while there is no significant disparity, continuous efforts are necessary to maintain and enhance this balance, particularly by addressing the lowest-rated areas such as specific student services awareness, individual responsibility for VMGO realization, and orientation processes (Clemente et al., 2021; Aquino & Rivano, 2022; Dolipas et al., 2022; Sanchez & Olvido, 2024). This comprehensive approach can help reinforce the overall effectiveness and integration of the Student Affairs and Services framework at San Isidro College (Tan & Prado, 2020; Tan, 2021).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The study reveals that students are well aware of the VMGO of the office of SAS, with high ratings for overall awareness, acceptance, understanding, relevance, and dissemination. Despite the strong general awareness, specific areas such as student welfare services and regular VMGO presentations during orientations require further attention. The acceptance and understanding of the VMGO effectively inspire student commitment, although students need more guidance on their roles in achieving these goals. The relevance of the VMGO is recognized, especially in supporting marginalized groups, but orientation processes need enhancement. Dissemination is effective through digital platforms, but more inclusive communication strategies are necessary for special student groups. The ANOVA test confirms no significant difference in the perception of awareness, acceptance and understanding, relevance, and dissemination, indicating a balanced approach in the SAS framework office. The results' consistent perception across all dimensions underscores the need for continuous efforts to maintain and improve the integration of the VMGO, particularly by addressing the identified gaps.

In conclusion, the results suggest that while the SAS office has effectively communicated its VMGO to the student body, there are areas for improvement that can further enhance student engagement and support. Addressing the gaps in specific student services awareness, individual responsibility for VMGO realization, and orientation processes will strengthen the overall integration of the SAS framework, ensuring it meets the diverse needs of all students at San Isidro College.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study's results recommend that orientation programs could be enhanced to introduce students to the college environment and the VMGO. Developing comprehensive orientation sessions that provide detailed information about the vision, mission, goals, and objectives, along with the available services and how to access them, can help students feel more informed and integrated from the outset. Ensuring these programs are inclusive and welcoming to all students, particularly those from marginalized groups, could foster a stronger sense of belonging and support.

Additionally, improving communication strategies could ensure that all student demographics are adequately informed about the VMGO. Leveraging various platforms, such as social media, the school website, and targeted outreach efforts, could help tailor messages to meet the specific needs of different student groups, including Indigenous peoples, persons with disabilities, and solo parents. This approach would ensure that every segment of the student population is included. Moreover, it might be advantageous to develop initiatives that empower students to take an active role in realizing the VMGO. Workshops, mentorship programs, and student-led projects that align with the VMGO could foster a sense of ownership and responsibility among students, encouraging them to contribute actively to the college's goals and objectives.

Correspondingly, the office could consider increasing the frequency and depth of VMGO presentations during orientations and assemblies. Providing regular updates and engaging students in discussions about the VMGO could reinforce their understanding and commitment, ensuring that the vision, mission, goals, and objectives remain at the forefront of their college experience. Lastly, further studies could explore the long-term impact of enhanced orientation and communication strategies on student engagement and success. This study could include longitudinal tracking of student outcomes to assess how improved integration of the VMGO influences their academic performance, retention rates, and overall college experience. Furthermore, investigating the effectiveness of empowerment initiatives in fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility among students could provide valuable insights for further enhancing the office of the SAS framework.

REFERENCE

- Aquino, J. M. D. R., & Rivano, E. (2022). Awareness, Acceptance, and Understanding of University Vision, Mission, College Goals and BSIT Objectives of Laguna State Polytechnic University Stakeholders towards its VMGO. *ASEAN J. Educ*, 8(1), 26-33.
- Astin, A. W. (1984). Student involvement: A developmental theory for higher education. *Journal of college student personnel*, 25(4), 297-308.
- Cascolan, H. M. S., & Venture, M. J. A. B. (2019). Awareness and acceptability of the Pangasinan State University vision, mission, campus goals and the program objectives. *Journal of Education, Management and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 73-77.
- Center for School Change (n.d.). *Vision and Mission* <https://centerforschoolchange.org/publications/minnesota-charter-school-handbook/vision-and-mission/>
- Clemente, B. G., & Clemente, R. C. (2022). Awareness and acceptability of the CSU philosophy, vision, mission, goals, and objectives, and the graduate school philosophy, vision, mission, goals, and objectives. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(5), 5598-5617.

- Clemente, B. G., Clemente, R. C., Calanoga, M. C. M., Lavarias, G. M., Aquino, I. P., & Bistayan, P. A. (2021). Multisectoral Awareness and Acceptability of the VMGO and Meaning Making of the Vision and Mission. *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 5(S2), 956-973. <https://doi.org/10.21744/lingcure.v5nS2.1615>
- Constantino, J. A., Sison, M. H., Gabriel, E. C., & Vega, M. T. C. (2020). Perception, awareness, acceptance and understanding of NEUST-SIC community towards its vision, mission, goals and objectives. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering, Management and Science*, 6(7), 335-346. <https://dx.doi.org/10.22161/ijaems.67.6>
- Dolipas, B. B., Buasen, J. A., Lubrica, M. A. B., Ocampo, P. S., Pakipac, K. B., Sajise, M. T., & Valentin, P. M. (2022). Assessment of the university vision, goals, mission and program objectives: a management protocol for quality assurance. *Athens journal of business & economics*, 8(2), 139-158. <https://doi.org/10.30958/ajbe.8-2-3>.
- Escolano, E. (2021). Awareness and acceptability on the institution's vision, mission, goals and quality policy in one state college in the Philippines. *Journal of Education, Management and Development Studies*, 1(2), 10-24. <https://doi.org/10.52631/jemds.v1i2.28>
- Evans, N. J., Forney, D. S., Guido, F. M., Patton, L. D., & Renn, K. A. (2009). *Student development in college: Theory, research, and practice*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Lacaba, L., & Pelicano, A. (2016). Awareness and acceptability of the vision, mission, goals and objectives of Eastern Samar State University. *International Journal of Innovation and Research in Educational Sciences*, 3(6), 432-435.
- LePeau, L. (2015). A grounded theory of academic affairs and student affairs partnerships for diversity and inclusion aims. *The Review of Higher Education*, 39(1), 97-122. <https://doi.org/10.1353/rhe.2015.0044>
- Ludeman, R., Osfield, K.J., Hidalgo, E.I., Oste, D., and Wang, H. (2009). *Student affairs and services in higher education: global foundations, issues and best practices* [Paper Presentation] 2009 World Conference on Higher Education - The New Dynamics of Higher Education and Research for Societal Change and Development, Paris, 2009
- MacDonald, G. P. (2013). Theorizing university identity development: multiple perspectives and common goals. *Higher Education*, 65, 153-166. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-012-9526-3>
- Sanchez, J. M., & Olvido, M. M. (2024). Awareness, dissemination, and acceptability of VMGO in an education graduate school of a state university in Central Visayas, Philippines. *Journal of Education and Innovation*, 26(2), 13-25.
- Talosa, A., Licopit, D. G., Macadangdang, K., Utanes, N., & Cabalbag, A. (2021). The stakeholders' level of awareness and attainability of Cagayan State University vision and mission and graduate school goals and objectives. *International Journal of Arts, Sciences and Education*, 1(3), 1-14. <https://ijase.org/index.php/ijase/article/view/28>
- Tan, M.R., (2021). *Evaluating of Student Affairs and Services on Student's Academic Performance: A Model for Standardization*. (Ph.D. dissertation). Liceo de Cagayan University, Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25877.55520>
- Tan, M. R. S., & Prado, N. I. (2020). Evaluation of Student Affairs and Services on Students' Academic Performance: A Model. *Liceo Journal of Higher Education Research*, 16(2), 116-134. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7828/ljher.v16i2.1380>
- UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization). (2002). *The role of student affairs and services in higher education: A practical manual for developing, implementing and assessing student affairs programs and services*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Villanca, A. A., Binayao, B. S., Caterial, M. Z. D., & Ablanque, V. C. (2020). Assessing the vision, mission, goals and objectives of a state university in Southern Philippines. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 5(10), 189-194.